

ON ONE BOUNDARY PROBLEM FOR A PARABOLIC-HYPERBOLIC EQUATION OF THE THIRD ORDER, WHEN THE CHARACTERISTIC OF THE FIRST ORDER OPERATOR IS PARALLEL TO THE YORDINATE AXIS

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Annotation: *In the present paper, one boundary value problem third is posed and studied for a-order parabolic-hyperbolic equation in a quadrangular domain with two lines of type change.*

I. Introduction.

Many problems in physics, engineering, mechanics and other areas require the study of equations of mixed, composite and mixed-composite types.

Fundamental research into mixed equations of the second order of elliptic-hyperbolic type began to be studied by the Italian mathematician Tricomi in the 20s of the last century [1].

After that, many different problems for equations of these types began to be investigated. A review of theoretical and applied research is given in the works and books of A.V. Bitsadze [2, 3], L. Bers [4], M.M. Smirnov [5], and also in the books of M.S., T.D. Dzhuraeva [7].

Research into equations of elliptic-parabolic, parabolic-hyperbolic types began in the 1950s and 1960s. In 1959, I.M. Gel'fand [8] pointed out the need for joint consideration of equations in one part of the domain of parabolic, and the other part - of hyperbolic types. He gives an example related to the movement of gas in a channel surrounded by a porous medium: in the channel, the movement of gas is described by the wave equation, outside it - by the diffusion equation.

Then, in the 1970s and 1980s, they began to study various problems for equations of the third and higher orders of the parabolic-hyperbolic type. Such problems were studied mainly by T. D. Dzhuraev and his students (for example, see [9]-[13]).

II. Formulation of the problem

Let us be given a quadrangular area G on the plane xOy with vertices at the points $D(-1;0)$, $C(2,0)$, $B_0(1;1)$, $A_0(0,1)$ and let the area G have the form $G = G_1 \cup G_2 \cup G_3 \cup J_1 \cup J_2$, where G_1 – the rectangle with vertices at the points $A(0;0)$, $B(1;0)$, $B_0(1,1)$, $A_0(0,1)$; G_2 – triangle with vertices at points $A(0;0)$, $D(-1;0)$, $A_0(0,1)$; G_3 – triangle with vertices at points $B(1;0)$, $B_0(1,1)$, $C(2,0)$; J_1 – open segment with vertices at points $A(0;0)$, $A_0(0,1)$; J_2 – open segment with vertices at points $B(1;0)$, $B_0(1,1)$.

In the area G , consider the equation

$$\left(b \frac{\partial}{\partial y} + c\right)(Lu) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{where } b, c \in R, Lu \equiv \begin{cases} u_{1xx} - u_{1y}, & (x, y) \in G_1, \\ u_{ixx} - u_{iyy}, & (x, y) \in G_i \ (i = 2, 3, 4). \end{cases}$$

For equation (1), the following problem is posed:

Problem 1. Find a function $u(x, y)$ that 1) is continuous in $\bar{G}$ and $G \setminus J_1 \setminus J_2 \setminus J_3$ has continuous derivatives involved in equation (1), and u_x , u_y and u_{yy} are continuous up to a part of the boundary of the region G specified in the boundary conditions; 2) satisfies equation (1) in the region $G \setminus J_1 \setminus J_2 \setminus J_3$; 3) satisfies the following boundary conditions:

$$u(x, 0) = f_1(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1, \quad (2)$$

$$u_y(x, 0) = f_2(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1, \quad (3)$$

$$u(x, 0) = f_3(x), \quad -1 \leq x \leq 0, \quad (4)$$

$$u_y(x, 0) = f_4(x), \quad -1 \leq x \leq 0, \quad (5)$$

$$u_{yy}(x, 0) = f_5(x), \quad -1 < x < 0, \quad (6)$$

$$u(x, 0) = f_6(x), \quad 1 \leq x \leq 2, \quad (7)$$

$$u_y(x, 0) = f_7(x), \quad 1 \leq x \leq 2, \quad (8)$$

$$u_{yy}(x, 0) = f_8(x), \quad 1 < x < 2, \quad (9)$$

and 4) satisfies the following continuous gluing conditions:

$$u(+0, y) = u(-0, y) = \tau_1(y), \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1, \quad (10)$$

$$u_x(+0, y) = u_x(-0, y) = \nu_1(y), \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1, \quad (11)$$

$$u(1+0, y) = u(1-0, y) = \tau_2(y), \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1, \quad (12)$$

$$u_x(1+0, y) = u_x(1-0, y) = \nu_2(y), \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1. \quad (13)$$

Here f_i ($i = \overline{1,8}$), are given sufficiently smooth functions, and τ_1 , ν_1 , τ_2 , ν_2 are unknown yet sufficiently smooth functions to be determined.

Theorem. If $f_1 \in C^3[0,1]$, $f_3 \in C^3[-1,0]$, $f_6 \in C^3[1,2]$, $f_2 \in C^2[0,1]$, $f_4 \in C^2[-1,0]$, $f_7 \in C^2[1,2]$, $f_5 \in C^1[-1,0]$, $f_8 \in C^1[1,2]$, and the following matching conditions are satisfied: $\tau_1(0) = f_1(0) = f_3(0)$, $\tau_2(0) = f_1(1) = f_6(1)$, $\nu_1(0) = f_2(0) = f_4(0)$, $\nu_2(0) = f_2(1) = f_7(1)$, then Problem 1 admits a unique solution .

To prove this theorem, we rewrite equation (1) in the form

$$u_{1xx} - u_{1y} = \omega_1(x)e^{-\frac{c}{b}y}, \quad (x, y) \in G_1, \quad (14)$$

$$u_{ixx} - u_{iyy} = \omega_i(x)e^{-\frac{c}{b}y}, \quad (x, y) \in G_i \quad (i = 2, 3), \quad (15)$$

where $\omega_i(x)$ ($i=1,2,3$) are so far unknown sufficiently smooth functions.

First, we study Problem 1 in the domain G_2 . Passing in the equation (15) ($i = 2$) to the limit at $y \rightarrow 0$, due to (4) and (6) we find

$$\omega_2(x) = f_3''(x) - f_5(x), \quad -1 \leq x \leq 0.$$

Further, by the continuation method after long calculations and transformations, we arrive at the relation between the functions $\tau_1(y)$ and $\nu_1(y)$:

$$\nu_1(y) = \tau_1'(y) + \beta_1(y), \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1 \quad (16)$$

where $\beta_1(y)$ – known function.

Similarly, passing to the region G_3 , at $y \rightarrow 0$ from Eq. (15) ($i = 3$) we find function $\omega_3(x)$.

Using the continuation method, as in the area G_2 , we obtain the relation between the functions $\tau_2(y)$ and $\nu_2(y)$:

$$\nu_2(y) = -\tau_2'(y) + \beta_2(y), \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1 \quad (17)$$

where $\beta_2(y)$ – known function .

Next, move on to the area G_1 . Assuming in equation (14) $y \rightarrow 0$, due to (2) and (3), we find the function $\omega_1(x)$.

Now we write down the solution of equation (14) that satisfies conditions (2), (10), (12) (see [9]):

$$\begin{aligned} u_1(x, y) = & \int_0^y \tau_1(\eta) G_\xi(x, y; 0, \eta) d\eta - \int_0^y \tau_2(\eta) G_\xi(x, y; 1, \eta) d\eta + \\ & + \int_0^1 f_1(\xi) G(x, y; \xi, 0) d\xi - \int_0^y e^{-\frac{c}{b}\eta} d\eta \int_0^1 \omega_1(\xi) G(x, y; \xi, \eta) d\xi. \end{aligned}$$

Differentiating this solution with respect to x , we get:

$$u_{1x}(x, y) = -\int_0^y \tau_1'(\eta) N(x, y; 0, \eta) d\eta + \int_0^y \tau_2'(\eta) N(x, y; 1, \eta) d\eta +$$

$$+ \int_0^1 \tau_1'(\xi) N(x, y; \xi, 0) d\xi + \int_0^y e^{-\frac{c}{b}\eta} d\eta \int_0^1 \omega_1(\xi) N_\xi(x, y; \xi, \eta) d\xi, \text{ (eighteen)}$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} G(x, y; \xi, \eta) \\ N(x, y; \xi, \eta) \end{aligned} \right\} = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi(y-\eta)}} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \left\{ \exp\left[-\frac{(x-\xi-2n)^2}{4(y-\eta)}\right] \mp \exp\left[-\frac{(x+\xi-2n)^2}{4(y-\eta)}\right] \right\}.$$

Green's functions of the first and second boundary value problems for Eq. (14).

Assuming in (18) $x=0$ and $x=1$ we obtain two relations between the unknown functions $\tau_1(y)$, $v_1(y)$, $\tau_2(y)$ and $v_2(y)$.

Eliminating from these two relations and from (16), (17) the functions $v_1(y)$ and $v_2(y)$, we arrive at a system of Volterra integral equations of the second kind with respect to $\tau_1'(y)$ and $\tau_2'(y)$:

$$\tau_1'(y) + \int_0^y K_1(y, \eta) \tau_1'(\eta) d\eta + \int_0^y K_2(y, \eta) \tau_2'(\eta) d\eta = g_1(y), \quad (19)$$

$$\tau_2'(y) + \int_0^y K_3(y, \eta) \tau_2'(\eta) d\eta + \int_0^y K_4(y, \eta) \tau_1'(\eta) d\eta = g_2(y), \quad (20)$$

where $K_1(y, \eta)$, $K_2(y, \eta)$, $K_3(y, \eta)$, $K_4(y, \eta)$, $g_1(y)$, $g_2(y)$ – known functions, $K_1(y, \eta)$ and $K_3(y, \eta)$ have a weak singularity (with degree 1/2), while the functions $K_2(y, \eta)$, $K_4(y, \eta)$, $g_1(y)$ and $g_2(y)$ – are continuous functions.

Solving the system (19), (20), we find the functions $\tau_1'(y)$ and $\tau_2'(y)$, and thus the functions $v_1(y)$, $v_2(y)$, $u_2(x, y)$, $u_3(x, y)$ and $u_1(x, y)$.

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